

LISTENING TEXTS AND LISTENING STRATEGIES

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Abstract

Listening is a fundamental skill in language acquisition, serving as a cornerstone for effective communication and comprehension. This study explores the significance of listening texts and strategies in enhancing learners' ability to process and interpret spoken language. Listening texts, which include dialogues, monologues, and multimedia content, provide authentic contexts that expose learners to various accents, speech rates, and language structures. Listening strategies, such as predicting content, inferring meaning, and using contextual clues, help learners overcome comprehension barriers and improve their overall listening proficiency.

Key words

Listening comprehension, Authentic listening texts, Listening strategies, Language learning process, Spoken language input, Active listening skills, Language proficiency development, Communication competence, Strategy-based learning, Language pedagogy,

Authentic Listening

Definition: Engaging actively, empathetically, and with genuine interest in what the speaker is saying.

Characteristics: Focused Attention: The listener is fully present and avoids distractions.

Empathy: Shows understanding of the speaker's emotions and perspective.

Non-judgmental: Listens without forming premature opinions.

Interactive: Responds thoughtfully with clarifying questions or reflective statements.

Body Language: Maintains eye contact, nods, and uses facial expressions to show engagement.

Example: A manager listens attentively to an employee's concerns, paraphrases key points to ensure understanding, and asks follow-up questions.

Non-Authentic Listening

Definition: Listening in a superficial, distracted, or insincere manner without genuine interest in the speaker's message.

Characteristics: Distracted Attention: Multitasking or not fully present.

Judgmental: Forms opinions or assumptions while the other person is speaking.

Minimal Interaction: Provides surface-level responses like “Hmm” or “Okay” without real engagement.

Body Language: Avoids eye contact, appears disinterested, or fidgety.

Agenda-Driven: Focuses on their own thoughts rather than the speaker's.

Example: During a meeting, a team member nods while checking their phone and misses key details of the discussion.

Cognitive , Metacognitive, Socio-effective

1.Cognitive

cognitive domain is centered on mental processes involved in learning and thinking. This is often the first level of learning, focusing on processing information and acquiring skills.

Memory: Storing and recalling facts or experiences.

Attention: Focusing on relevant stimuli and filtering out distractions.

Problem-Solving: Using logic and reasoning to find solutions.

Critical Thinking: Analyzing and evaluating information or arguments.

Knowledge Acquisition: Learning and understanding new information.

Examples: Reading and comprehending a text.

Solving math problems.

Memorizing historical dates.

Analyzing the themes of a novel.

2. Metacognitive

Metacognition refers to "thinking about thinking" and involves higher-level processes that help individuals control their learning. It includes self-awareness, self-regulation, and reflection on one's thought processes.

Planning: Deciding how to approach a task (e.g., breaking it into smaller steps).

Monitoring: Tracking progress while performing a task (e.g., asking, "Am I understanding this correctly?").

Evaluating: Reflecting on the outcome (e.g., asking, "What worked well, and what didn't?").

Adaptation: Adjusting strategies to improve outcomes.

Examples: Before a test, a student creates a study schedule (planning).

While reading a chapter, they pause to summarize (monitoring).

After completing an assignment, they evaluate what strategies were effective (evaluating).

3. Socio-Affective

The socio-affective domain emphasizes the emotional and social aspects of learning. It acknowledges the importance of relationships, emotions, and interpersonal skills in facilitating effective learning.

Emotional Regulation: Managing feelings like frustration, anxiety, or motivation.

Empathy: Understanding and sharing the feelings of others.

Collaboration: Working effectively in teams or groups.

Communication: Expressing thoughts and listening actively.

Motivation: Maintaining a positive attitude toward learning.

Examples: Encouraging group projects to develop teamwork skills.

A teacher providing emotional support to help a student overcome learning anxiety.

1. Transactional Listening

Transactional listening is focused on exchanging information to accomplish a specific purpose or task. It is commonly seen in settings where efficiency, accuracy, and results are prioritized.

2. Intersectional Listening

Intersectional listening is rooted in the concept of intersectionality, a term coined by legal scholar Kimberlé Crenshaw to describe how various aspects of a person's identity (e.g., race, gender, class, ability) intersect and shape their experiences. This form of listening focuses on understanding the speaker's full context, including systemic and social influences.